

IMPROVING THE MAINTENANCE OF BELT CONVEYOR BELTS

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Annotation: In this article, the analysis of the current state of belt conveyor repair technology in the mining industry in the world and in our Republic is considered. Belt conveyors are analyzed for their time-consuming, productivity-affecting, and other methods of preparing belts for repair because they are mostly done by hand.

Keywords: Belt conveyors, rubber fabric belts, tensile strength, shovel conveyors, belting, synthetic, conveyor performance.

In recent years, the need for widespread use of belt conveyors in mining enterprises of Uzbekistan and the world is increasing, their advantages are based on many scientific works carried out in recent years.

The use of belt conveyors in open mines, their transportation of hard rocks in larger quantities compared to other types of conveyors, in turn, leads to an increase in operational productivity by 20-25%. In addition, the ease of automation of belt conveyors also increases the possibility of its use in open-pit mining operations.

The type of conveyor most commonly used in open-pit mining enterprises in our country today is a belt conveyor.

The main characteristics of belt conveyors include distance of transportation, lifting height from the location, length of the structure, turning radius, annual productivity, number of electric motors, power of electric motors, speed of movement in loaded and unloaded state, hardness of rock affecting the belt and volume of transported load. Figure 1.1 shows the main parts of a belt conveyor.

1 – tape; 2 - protective cover; 3 – electric drive; 4 – coupling;
5 - extension; 6 – drum; 7 – rama; 8 – roller

Figure 1.1. Belt conveyor

The analysis of operational indicators of belt conveyors shows that most of the belt conveyors used in mining enterprises work with low efficiency compared to the one indicated in the passport. The reason for this is the occurrence of unexpected stops during the work, the failure of the electric motors, the frequent breaking of the belts, the cutting of the board parts of the belts, and the leading drum rotating in place without pulling the belt.

The above-mentioned causes increase in the operating cost of belt conveyors and decrease in their efficiency.

Cutting and preparing the tape with the above specifications requires heavy manual labor and a lot of time from the working group.

At the same time, the preparation of the conveyor belt for manual cutting causes the following disadvantages:

- decrease in the annual productivity of the conveyor
- overhang of the tape on the rollers (if the folds of the tape are cut unevenly)
- load on electric motors
- it takes a lot of time to prepare the tape for cutting and splicing, etc

Therefore, it is not appropriate to use ordinary metal knives in the process of cutting the broken parts of the tapes. In the age of advanced techniques and technologies, it is necessary to create a new and modern device for cutting tapes, using

modern technologies to cut the broken parts of the tapes and prepare them for connection.

Figure 1.2 below shows a schematic view of the new tape cutting device we are proposing.

Figure 1.2. Side and front views of the tape cutting equipment

Preparing the cut parts of the belt for cutting by a newly developed rubber cutting device provides us with several conveniences.

First of all, until now, each connection point was manually cut and it took 1-2 hours to prepare for the connection, but with the help of the developed device, we will do this work in 30 minutes.

Secondly, by reducing the time spent on repair work, we can increase the annual productivity of the belt conveyor (bring it closer to the indicator specified in the technical description).

Thirdly, it is rare for the belts to be cut with precise dimensions to slip on the conveyor rollers, as a result of which our belts can run continuously for a long time.

Fourthly, we will get rid of the load on the electric motors as a result of the tapes going out on the rollers.

In conclusion, we can increase the annual productivity graph of belt conveyors by 10-15% based on the above-mentioned advantages.

If we apply this newly developed device to production, we will be able to improve the work efficiency of the conveyor transport while simplifying the work of the

workers maintaining the conveyor belts. In addition, the service life of the cut-to-size belt is longer than that of the hand-cut belt.

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